

COMPREHENSIVE MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF SYNERGISIS AND FILTRATION IN
BRYZA PRODUCTION TECHNOLOGY

Safarov Jasur Esirgapovich

prof., Tashkent State Technical University,

Sultanova Shakhnoza Abduvahitovna

prof., Deputy Mayor of Tashkent city

Ergasheva Zulfiya Kakhramanovna

Senior Lecturer, Tashkent State Technical University

Annotation. The article presents a comprehensive mathematical model of synergisis and filtration in the technology of brynza production using ultrasound.

Keywords: milk protein; process; multiphysical model; differential equation; mathematical modelling; experiment; speed; diagram; automation; whey;

Introduction. Brynza production is an important branch of the dairy industry. Increasing production efficiency and improving product quality requires the introduction of innovative technologies. In recent years, the use of ultrasonic vibrations in milk processing has been actively studied.

Ultrasound is a mechanical vibration with a frequency above 20 kHz. In the dairy industry, such vibrations can cause microcavitation, accelerate the diffusion of substances, and change the structure of milk proteins. Thanks to these properties, ultrasound can be used at various stages of the production of brined cheeses, including brynza.

The processes of separating the liquid phase from coagulable or structured materials, such as cottage cheese or brynza, can be described using various mathematical models [1,3]. The main approaches include:

- diffusion models based on Fick's equation for describing mass transfer;
- capillary models that take into account surface tension forces and capillary pressures;
- hydrodynamic models based on Darcy's law, which describes the filtration of liquid through a porous medium;
- empirical and semi-empirical relationships derived from experimental data.

Serum separation is the process of squeezing liquid out of a gel-like medium under external pressure or through internal molecular interactions. The mechanism is based on syneresis, which is the phase

separation of a system caused by the compression of a clot structure, during which water molecules and dissolved substances are pushed out [2,3,4].

At the macro level, the process can be represented as the filtration of liquid through a porous structure, where the flow of moisture obeys Darcy's law:

$$v = \frac{K}{\mu} \cdot \nabla P \quad (1)$$

Where v -is the filtration velocity; K -is the permeability of the material; μ -is the viscosity of the medium; ∇P -is the pressure gradient.

Fig. 1. Block diagram for calculating filtration velocity according to Darcy's law in MATLAB/Simulink

In self-pressing conditions, pressure is created by gravity and surface tension, whereas in ultrasonic processing, pressure is pulsating and localized, which significantly speeds up the process and is represented in computer implementation (for example, in the Simulink environment) as follows:

Approximate allocation function:

Fig. 2. Graph of energy absorbed by brynza cheese

The change in energy absorbed by the brynza structure directly depends on:

- ultrasound intensity;
- product properties (moisture content, density, structure);
- penetration coefficient.

Fig. 3. Graph of absorbed energy $E(t)$.

Analysis of the combined graph $T(t)$ and $\phi(t)$ allows:

To determine the optimal operating temperature;

To identify the inflection point at which the intensity of release decreases sharply;

Calculate the efficiency of the process based on the ratio of energy to moisture released.

The process of releasing whey from curd under the influence of ultrasound can be described as thermoacoustic desorption [4,6].

The most effective zone is the area where the temperature reaches 45-55 °C and the ultrasound intensity is 20-35 kHz.

Change in moisture content (serum fraction).

The mass fraction of whey in brynza decreased from an initial level of 62% to ~50% over 40 minutes of processing. The rate of moisture removal was highest in the first 10-20 minutes.

Fig. 4. Graph showing changes in the moisture content of brynza cheese at different ultrasonic treatment frequencies

An exponential decrease followed by saturation is observed.

Moisture desorption rate. The highest desorption rate was achieved at a temperature of 47-50 °C. Outside this range (above 60 °C), a decrease in efficiency was observed, which is associated with the compaction of the protein structure of brynza.

Fig. 5. Derivative of moisture content over time the peak occurs at 2-3 minutes, followed by a gradual slowdown.

Energy consumption. The total energy consumption of the installation was 60-70 kJ/kg of brynza. Energy was absorbed not only for phase transition, but also for cavitation processes, microstructural changes, and acoustic dispersion.

At the same time, the efficiency of moisture removal per unit of energy was higher compared to traditional methods, especially in the temperature range of 45-55 °C.

The model adequately describes the behavior of the system and allows key parameters to be predicted with high accuracy.

Computer implementation in the MATLAB/Simulink environment provided flexible configuration of processing modes.

The process of ultrasonic separation of whey from curd demonstrates high efficiency in terms of time, quality, and technological reliability [5].

Conclusion. An integrated multiphysical model has been developed to quantitatively describe the physicochemical processes occurring during the separation of whey from protein curds under the action of ultrasound. The model includes equations for mass transfer, filtration, heat transfer, phase transition, and acoustic energy. Below is a system of interrelated equations reflecting the dynamics of the main parameters of the process.

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